

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR
D.5.2 Capacity Building Seminars for LEARNTECH Accelerator
Community Report
30.4.2019

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D.5.2 Capacity Building Seminars for LEARNTECH Accelerator Community Report

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1. INTRODUCTION

LEA's main goals are to accelerate knowledge transfer, dialog and awareness raising of innovation procurement within the learning technology sector. Its strategy includes multiple activities in order to achieve these goals. This report focuses in one type of these activities — Capacity Building Seminars (CBS). CBS are being organised, within the LEA project, with the aim of engaging other stakeholders (especially procurers) into the LEARNTECH accelerator community and increasing their understanding on innovation procurement methods (PCP and PPI¹). During CBS, LEA Partners present an overview of PCP and PPI related issues and provide support materials that describe those issues in a more detailed way.

A first internal CBS was organised on 18-19 June 2018, in Halmstad - Sweden, for the LEA consortium members, to clarify and test the pre-requisites and key steps to design and implement an innovation procurement process. This first CBS served as a pilot to the next external CBS and provided the LEA Consortium valuable recommendations for the upcoming CBS (see deliverable 5.1 and short main recommendation on the following page).

In this report, we provide an overview of the external CBS organised to date, describing the contexts in which they were organised, as well as their specific content, and the feedback received from the attendees. Based on the results achieved with the Satisfaction Surveys and the opinions

¹ PCP: Pre-Commercial Procurement; PPI: Public Procurement in Innovation.

provided by the presenters, we finalise the report with some recommendations and guidelines for future CBS.

Guidelines for future CBS

- Try to simplify. PCP and PPI are not easy to understand, so presentation must try to focus on the main topics in an easy common language, using visual graphics and examples whenever possible;
- PCP and PPI must be presented following a step by step methodology, from the preparation until the execution;
- Having independent experts is crucial to reinforce knowledge, and having external opinions is always a plus;
- Always try to have some previous experiences from other Projects on PCP and PPI, to collect lessons learnt;
- Save some time at the end of the presentations for Questions and Answers – participation is very welcome and benefits the both sides;
- Try to have shorter presentation covering more themes, to give participants a general overview of the whole process;
- Take into consideration the levels of knowledge that participants might have on the PCP and PPI topics;
- Try, whenever possible to have the presentations available or to be assisted online, for those who cannot be physically present.

Key message 1: The innovation procurement process and the responsible procurers must be well prepared. Seminars must be prepared to address participants with different levels of knowledge, trying to make the effort of leveraging the ones that know less about PCP and PPI, and knowing that this is always a continuous learning process until the end of the project.

Key message 2: Every consortium must capitalise their internal expertise. Nevertheless, if there is a lack of expertise, independent experts must be invited to pass along their experience and knowledge.

Key message 3: Investing in innovation procurement is not only challenging, but also requires a lot of preparation and time. Some tasks might look extremely time consuming and resource intensive, however, this is the price of being a pioneer in the field of innovation procurement in education.

[Retrieved from Deliverable 5.1]

2. CBS FOR LEARNTech ACCELERATOR COMMUNITY

Two external CBS were organised, the first one in Turin (Italy) and the second one in Valencia (Spain). Both were organised within the framework of larger events, in order to get the attention and involvement of the highest number of participants possible. Their content and structure took into account the recommendations resulting from the evaluation of the first CBS:

- the topics discussed were adjusted to each context, trying to address the different levels of knowledge that the public might have on the PCP and PPI;
- the themes covered were diverse and offered a general overview on the PCP and PPI processes;
- the contents were presented in a clear and simple format;
- both CBS were also open to Questions and Answers from the participants;
- after the CBS the participants received a satisfaction survey to give their opinion about the event.

2.1 CBS at *Festival dell'Educazione* in Turin, Italy

The first external CBS was held on 30 November 2018, at the *Festival dell'Educazione* (Festival of Education) in Turin, Italy (see image 1). The Festival is organised by the Municipality of Turin, with the contribution of the University of Turin and other Italian universities, and, in 2018, it reached its 3rd edition. Under the theme “For a creative, critical and civic thought”, the Festival sought to cover multiple subjects within the education sector.²

² More information about the *Festival dell'Educazione* can be consulted in the following website: <https://www.festivaleducazione.net>

Image 1 – LEA CBS in the Programme of Festival dell'Educazione

WORKSHOP
Venerdì 30 Novembre

WORKSHOP

ORE 10.30 - 12.30

CAPACITY BUILDING SU APPALTI PUBBLICI DI INNOVAZIONE PER IL MONDO DELLA SCUOLA – W24 OPEN INCET – via Cigna 96/17, Torino

Il workshop mira a coinvolgere stakeholder locali e nazionali in un confronto sull'evoluzione in ambito scolastico del Public Procurement finalizzato all'innovazione nella didattica, con particolare attenzione agli strumenti dell'appalto pre-commerciale, dell'appalto di soluzioni innovative e del partenariato per l'innovazione, anche nel quadro di una progettazione orientata a cogliere le opportunità offerte dai finanziamenti europei.

parole chiave
didattica innovativa - acquisti pubblici - finanziamenti europei

interviene
Sara Bedin, Independent expert on innovation procurement PCP Specialist - EAFIP (European Assistance for Innovation Procurement)

modalità di partecipazione
Iscrizioni sul sito www.learntechaccelerator.eu/festival-delleducazione-torino

Source : <https://www.festivaleducazione.net/programma/>

Sara Bedin (LEA consortium member) was the main organiser of the CBS developed at this event. The CBS was entitled “Capacity Building on Public Procurement in Innovation for the world of school” and introduced the audience to PCP and PPI, explaining the basic concept behind procurement, citing advantages for public stakeholders and for users, when using procurement in acquiring new learning technologies. Specifically, the following topics were presented and discussed:

- Innovation policy mix;
- Understanding Innovation Procurement procedures, instruments and approaches;
- Understanding the PCP legal framework and exemption regime;
- How to manage and design the PCP.

At this CBS, 25 participants were present, all Italian, so it was decided to have the seminar in Italian, since it could be beneficial, making the participant feel more comfortable in asking questions and understanding

every aspect in their mother language. The audience was very interested in the topics discussed and asked several questions. Sara Bedin answered the questions, providing practical examples from the field, where PCP and PPI are already in use.

Image 2 – Pictures of the LEA CBS at the Festival dell'Educazione

Image 3 – Feedback of an attendee to the LEA CBS at the Festival dell'Educazione

Source: <https://www.facebook.com/329773914093469/posts/456163508121175>

2.2 CBS at INTED2019 in Valencia, Spain

The second external CBS was held on 11 March 2019, at the 13th annual International Technology, Education and Development Conference (INTED2019) in Valencia, Spain (see image 4). INTED is one of the largest international education conferences for lecturers, researchers, technologists and professionals from the educational sector where more than 700 experts from 80 countries get together to present their projects and share their knowledge on teaching and learning methodologies and innovations on educational technology.³

Image 4 – LEA CBS in the Programme of INTED2019

This LEA CBS was entitled “Innovation Procurement to steer user-driven Innovations for Digital Learning” and was moderated by INOVA+ and SERN.

³ More information about INTED 2019 can be consulted in the following website: <https://iated.org/inted/>

Taking into account the potential audience of INTED, LEA partners considered it appropriate to not only discuss topics around the PCP and PPI processes, but also dedicate more time to describe and explain the work of LEA project, in order to get a better understanding from the audience on what was being presented. The session explored several topics, each one presented by LEA project partners:

- Sara Bedin and INOVA+ provided a presentation about the innovation procurement and tools for steering the market towards innovative solutions for education within the EU legal framework (PPI and PCP);
- Konnevesi Municipality and Viladecans Municipality introduced their approaches, experiences, differences and similarities;
- Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg presented the methodology and results from a needs analysis for ICT in teaching and learning conducted within LEA Project;
- University of Jyväskylä and University of Oulu made a presentation about procurement of innovative technologies in the educational sector such as Artificial Intelligence, Robotics or Virtual Reality;
- University of Oulu presented also how to implement these emerging technologies in learning and what goals can be achieved.

The seminar was accepted into the programme of the INTED annual conference 2019 as a special session, and due to this there was no pre-registration to the session, since participants were free to choose the session from the overall INTED programme. As such, an estimated 20-25 participants attended the session (but a precise list is not available).

Image 5 – Pictures of the LEA CBS at the INTED 2019

Summary of the Topics discussed during CBS at INTED 2019

INNOVATION PROCUREMENT TO STEER USER-DRIVEN INNOVATIONS FOR DIGITAL LEARNING: PRESENTING THE LEA PROJECT

Org.: INOVA+ and SERN

Understanding innovation procurement: tools to steer the market towards innovative solutions for education (Sara Bedin and INOVA+)

What has been the results of 30 years of supply-side incentives?

The intention is to discuss why supply-side innovations incentives typically fail to overcome “market failure”, revealing a negative crowding-out effect.

How a change in perspective is needed to move from traditional “push” and “market-driven” strategies to more effective “pull” and “really demand-driven”?

Following the logic of traditional tendering and contracting, if the public procurer decides to purchase innovative solutions, it must take on board all the technological risk of the supply. Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) and the complementary Public procurement of

innovation (PPI), are aimed to filter the risk of complex investments while enabling risk-benefit sharing mechanism.

Innovation procurement is an end-to-end process substantiated on a contract capable to enable all the potential benefits from innovation and competition, as well as contributes to breaking down the barriers to the adoption of innovative products and services linked to the historical advantages of solutions already available on the market while sending a clear signal (also) for private users.

The EU legal framework and instruments for innovation public procurement are going to be presented, demonstrating which opportunities they provide for optimally achieving the goal of enhancing competitiveness and efficiency in public spending, as well as to open the discussion on inter-administrative cooperation, exploring the additional consequences deriving from the perspective of cross-border procurement and the several layers of legal provisions involved interplay.

Aligned with the experience gathered on the participation of IMAILE (Innovative Methods for Award Procedures of ICT learning in Europe), the first Pre-Commercial Procurement project in Europe in the field of Education and Technology and now the current participation on the LEA (Learning Technology Accelerator) project whose goal is to accelerate knowledge transfer, dialogue and awareness raising of innovative procurement within the learning technology sector, there will be a particular focus on the innovation procurement action under the education sector.

Keywords: innovation procurement, PCP, PPI, education, incentives.

Two different procurers: Viladecans (Spain) and Konnevesi (Finland) – Similar Visions of Digital Learning (Konnevesi Municipality and Viladecans Municipality)

Konnevesi and Viladecans are two very different procurement partners. The northern village of Konnevesi hosts 2800 inhabitants and the school centre has around 250 students. However, the level of technical equipment is quite high and modern for a school of this size, with big HD screens in every classroom and plenty of student laptop devices for everyday use. Viladecans is a 66.500 inhabitants city in the metropolitan area of Barcelona. Education is a priority for Viladecans, and even though municipalities in Spain do not have the competence on education, the city works hard to ensure the educational success of its students. In this respect, Viladecans has provided all city classrooms with interactive whiteboards and fiber optics and has developed numerous initiatives to foster educational innovation. Nevertheless, what projects such as IMAILE and LEA have shown is, that despite the differences, the needs of teachers and students are very similar.

IMAILE was a Pre-Commercial Procurement Project (PCP) in the education sector. Konnevesi and Viladecans were two of the four initial procurement partners, who challenged the market to develop innovative technology supporting the identified needs in European schools. The research and development in the project resulted in two pilots of smart and innovative Personal Learning Environments (PLEs), offering learning analytics provided by intelligent tutoring systems to primary and secondary schools. The results of the project show,

that the PCP has provided pedagogical, financial and technological benefits.

The LEA project is making use of the public procurement and its potential purchase power. LEA aims at reforming traditional education systems to achieve better learning results for students. The steps in achieving this goal are conducting a needs analysis, preparing the first cross-border European PPI (Public Procurement of Innovation) and PCP, facilitating the dialogue between the demand and supply sides and raising awareness about the many benefits of innovation procurement. The LEA project is currently preparing a PPI on the increased demand of personalised learning. The future goal is to prepare a new PCP on innovative learning technology solutions based on the needs of European schools in spring 2019.

In these projects, the role of Konnevesi and Viladecans as procurement partners, was and is to evaluate and report. The procurement partners play a key role in carrying out the needs analysis in their respective schools and observing the current status of education. The procurement partners list their hopes and needs for the project and test the personalised learning platforms together with the suppliers.

Konnevesi and Viladecans have both taken part in the IMAILE and LEA projects. However, they are two very different procurement partners from different procuring cultures. The differences could be seen in, for example, teacher participation and the know-how of educational technology. What IMAILE and LEA have shown, is how similar the educational needs are, despite the different baselines. The approach might be different, but the demands of teachers and students remain the same in both countries/schools.

The benefits of being a procurement partner in an EU funded project for education development have been various. For example, the use of technology in education and highlighting one's own assets, are amongst the many gains. In addition, the contacts in partnering project countries and in the field of digital learning platform suppliers can be utilized in various future occasions.

Keywords: LEA, IMAILE, procurement, digital learning, cooperation.

Needs analysis for ICT in Teaching and Learning (Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg)

The use of digital learning technology has great potential for the school sector. It can promote individual and lifelong learning via the use of special learning environments and prepare content in a form that would be difficult or impossible to implement with conventional means. This is accompanied by new methodological approaches that enable or simplify forms of collaborative work and support different types of learners.

But despite the great amount of different ICT solutions on the market to be used in our classrooms, we still find a low use of technology to perform innovative teaching and creative learning in the European classrooms (see [1], [2]). For the EU-funded project "Learning Technology Accelerator (LEA)", a needs analysis has been executed to identify what teachers and students' actual needs are. Qualitative and quantitative methods in the form of face-to-face-workshops with students and teachers and online questionnaires have been used.

While focusing on the main actors, our approach was to not directly ask them about what

they need, but what they think are barriers that limit the exploitation of the full potential of learntech for use in schools, and about the skills they have. From these findings, the needs are derived that are necessary to overcome the barriers.

The research has been concentrated around the following questions:

- What skills do students/teachers need to use digital teaching and learning tools?
- What are the barriers for students/teachers when using digital teaching and learning tools?

In order to answer these questions, a quantitative survey for students and teachers has been developed and conducted in five European countries with almost 300 teachers and more than 900 students participating. In this paper, we present our answers for the questions.

Keywords: ICT, in education, personal learning environment, needs analysis for ict, survey for teachers and students.

References:

- [1] Lang, M. Lounaskorpi, P. Pardo, A., D 6.1 State of the Art in Personal Learning Environments; EU-project IMAILE 2014, <http://www.imaile.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/IMAILE-Recommendations-SoA-part-D6.1-Final-.pdf>
- [2] Survey of schools: ICT in education, Final Report for European Commission 2013, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/news/survey-schools-ict-education>

AI, Robotics, VR – How to make cost effective and sustainable procurement decisions for future technologies in municipalities and schools? (University of Jyväskylä and University of Oulu)

Learning technologies' procurement can be a challenging task for the buyer organisation. Municipalities and schools buy software or hardware, which turn out to be difficult to use (Clements & Wallin, 2017). The educational sector is also behind in utilising innovative cutting-edge technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics or virtual reality, in comparison to more commercial fields (Gülbahar, 2007). Public organisations are not as attractive customers to technology suppliers, due to the slow decision-making processes and tight budgets. Despite the barriers in the field: learning analytics and computational thinking could be the answer to support students preparing to the 21st century in the society where robots take care of many of the jobs we are used to. Personalised learning environments of 2018 are not using these new technology innovations in their full potential (Sjöden, 2017).

Two-part innovation procurement methodology has been developed to bridge the gap between technology suppliers and buyers, with the potential to develop new solutions to the market, corresponding to users' needs. Pre-commercial procurement (PCP) is the first step of this challenge with the aim of launching a call for tender first to investigate ideas meeting the challenge at hand. European commission co-funded IMAILE- project (Bel & al, 2014) took the PCP instrument and conducted the innovation procurement process in four countries (Finland, Sweden, Germany and Spain) in 2014-2018 with the outcome that solutions created in the IMAILE are now reaching first customers due to this also new jobs in the Learntech market. The procurement in a PCP project is for research and development only, with the idea that the municipalities and schools could then join together later to form the common demand and the second stage of innovation procurement methodology, the public procurement of innovation (PPI) project, which the expanded consortium is now preparing.

In the PLEASE PPI preparation (Wallin et al., 2018), seven countries (with Portugal, Italy and Hungary joining as additional to IMAILE procurers) compared their needs and barriers for future learning technologies. 1300 students and teachers answered questionnaires and workshops were held in schools to study the end-users needs for future learning technologies across Europe (Lang et al., 2018). The results of the needs analysis clearly show that there is a need for an AI enhanced personalised learning environment solution which would answer to the societal problems of saving teachers time, motivating students to actively reach their learning goals as well as detecting school drop-outs early. Southern and Northern parts of Europe differ in the policies within schools radically: In Finland and Sweden, students are encouraged to bring their own devices to school and therefore the future solutions should work on these devices. In Italy, Spain and Portugal, it is forbidden to bring your smart phone into the classroom. Despite of the differences, the needs analysis conducted showed that common demand within Europe exists and innovative solutions should be developed together with the end-users to meet it (Lang et al., 2018).

Keywords: innovation, procurement, pre-commercial procurement, public procurement, learning technologies, artificial intelligence, personalised learning environments.

Are we currently moving from the age of mobilism to age of artificial intelligence, learning analytics and robotics? How to couple emergent technology with learning and teaching? (University of Oulu)

The world is now in the age of mobilism and entering the age of artificial intelligence, learning analytics and robotics. New technology tools fit more readily and naturally into our lives; increasingly broad, inexpensive, and easy access to internet wireless devices and a variety of web-based personal publishing and social software tools have made computing truly a ubiquitous and “continuous” part of our lives. What is important is the fact that essentially anyone who wants a mobile device can afford to purchase one. Furthermore, the adoption of mobile devices has been quite rapid, as smartphone sales surpassed global PC shipments for the first time in history in 2010, and after that sales has surpassed those of feature phones many times.

We are using in our daily life a plethora of context-aware tools. Such tools are built on by following contemporary human–computer interaction paradigms (Bluetooth beacons, RFID tags, QR codes, Augmented intelligence, GPS, etc.), which are now mainstream in current mobile devices, navigators, smart watches and other IoT devices. The just-in-time and contextualised information afforded by these devices can serve as evidence to support partially formed ideas and misunderstandings, to trigger comparison with previously stored data on the devices, and to support an inquiry process or dialogue in situ. These affordances are enabling us to prepare instructional designs based on the ideas suggested almost a decade ago by Roschelle and Pea in their seminal paper on wireless learning devices.

Emerging technology should be used so that it fulfils basic educational goal:

- 1) develop responsible citizens;
- 2) develop lifelong learners;

- 3) develop basic knowledge and literacy;
- 4) develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

However, it is not an easy task because there are major challenges in implementing that ubiquitous and pervasive technology in classrooms. The first challenge is the large learning gap among learners in the classroom, which makes classroom curriculum difficult to fulfil and cater to each individual learners' learning. The second challenge is the fact that the burden of learning and using technology usually lies on the teachers. Proper training and support has to be available and provided to in-service and pre-service teachers. The third challenge is the teacher centered model of teaching and learning. In other words, in order to support the use of (emergent) technology in the classrooms, the existing curriculum in schools should be restructured and teachers should be rewarded. Fourth, more attention should be made on the use of technology instead of technology itself.

To address 21st century challenges and opportunities new designs and possibilities, such as user modelling, mobile devices and networks, rich interfaces and interfaces including gamification and intelligent systems and educational data mining should be used to:

- 1) personalise education;
- 2) assess students' learning in individual and group tasks;
- 3) diminish boundaries;
- 4) develop alternative teaching strategies and learning designs;
- 5) Enhance roles of stakeholders; and to address policy changes just like Woolf has argued.

In this presentation, the recent research results and contemporary technological advances are explored together in order to couple emergent technology and learning together.

Keywords: emergent technology, mobile devices, artificial intelligence, robotics, learning analytics, learning, teaching.

2.3 LEA webinars

Following the recommendations and the suggestions given on the first internal CBS, a different format of seminars was created, not to replace the physical CBS, but to give the interested stakeholders another option to accelerate their knowledge on innovation procurement, namely within the field of learning technology. LEA Webinars allow not only the capacity building of LEA community, but also a channel for supply & demand dialogue where stakeholders and meet and discuss regardless of their location.

Concerning this, a series of thematic webinars were created, initiated on September 2018, with a periodicity of two webinars per month. To date, 12

webinars have been presented, with the duration of 20-40 minutes each, usually held as 10:30 CET on Wednesday. The webinars series will continue to be held until the end of 2020 (with a break during summertime).

All the webinars are available on LEA's website:

(<https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/webinars/>)

and on LEA's YouTube channel:

(<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpqlRr9iLn1jBOPzaGoZ33w>).

Around 10-20 participants joined each online webinar on the day it was delivered. As they are available online, and to date, webinars have been watched more than 600 times, with an average of 52 person per webinar.

The following webinars were already presented:

- **Webinar 1:** 19 September 2018

Topic: **What is innovation procurement?**

Experts: Ellinor Wallin (EU Projekt Konsult) and Kati Clements (JYU)

LEA Webinar 1, What is innovation procurement

- **Webinar 2:** 03 October 2018

Topic: **Learntech 2018: AI, VR, robotics**

Experts: Seinäjoki City Councillor Mikko Muilu and Oulu City Councillor Dr. Jari Laru

18-10-2018 at 11:19:56.png

WEBINAR SERIES

lea Learning Technology Accelerator

Experts today:
Mikko Muilu, University of Jyväskylä
Dr. Jari Laru, University of Oulu

Webinar 2: Learntech Trends 2018

- 1.Virtual Reality
- 2.Robotics
- 3.Artificial Intelligence

Listen to the experts here: (18min)
https://youtu.be/u5PPUX1xR_g

Post your questions or comments to the chat box ->

Attendees (11): Kati Clements, Matti (2), Kati Clements, Mike, Jari Laru, Jari Laru

Chat (Hidden): Kati Clements: Hi guys, as in the previous webinar - post your questions to the chat box while listening to the recording here. Kati Clements: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zGtK5vU0BV8&feature=youtu.be> Daniela: yes Daniela: yes (can hear you) Daniela: hi

- **Webinar 3:** 17 October 2018

Topic: **Understanding the needs of the Demand: Municipalities & Schools.**

Experts: I. Capella Munar, S. Dominguez, P. Huuska, H. Sahlberg

WEBINAR SERIES

lea Learning Technology Accelerator

Experts today:
Paula Huuska, Hanna Konnevesi high school rector, Finland
Sonia Dominguez & Isabel Capella Munar Viladecans City Council project officer, Spain

Webinar 3: Understanding the Needs of Learn tech procurement: Municipalities & Schools

1. Listen to the experts here:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zGtK5vU0BV8&feature=youtu.be>
2. Post your questions to the chat box

Attendees (11): Kati Clements, Matti (2), Kati Clements, Mike, Jari Laru, Jari Laru, Jari Laru, Jari Laru, Jari Laru, Jari Laru, Jari Laru

Chat (Hidden): Kati Clements: Hi guys, as in the previous webinar - post your questions to the chat box while listening to the recording here. Kati Clements: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zGtK5vU0BV8&feature=youtu.be> Daniela: yes Daniela: yes (can hear you) Daniela: hi

- **Webinar 4:** Wednesday, 14 November 2018

Topic: **Suppliers' experience of PCP - Case Almerin**

Expert: Teemu Laitinen

LEA Webinar 4: Suppliers' experience of PCP - Case Almerin

- **Webinar 5:** Wednesday, 28 November 2018

Topic: **Professional competences required to utilize innovative technologies**

Expert: Rita Freudenberg

LEA Webinar 5: Professional competences required to utilize innovative technologies

- **Webinar 6:** Wednesday, 12 December 2018

Topic: **Understanding the legal aspects of joined vs. coordinated innovation procurement**

Experts: Marta Coto and Sara Bedin

LEA Webinar 6: Understanding the legal aspects of joined vs. coordinated innovation procurement

- **Webinar 7:** Wednesday, 09 January 2019

Topic: **Towards Easy Virtual Reality Content Creation**

Experts: Jarmo Tanskanen / Visumo corporation

LEA Webinar 7: Towards Easy Virtual Reality Content Creation

- **Webinar 8:** Live from BETT - Wed., 23 Jan. 2019

Topic: **Special edition on LEA @BETT 2019**

Experts: Kati Clements and Mikko Muilu are reporting from the BETT show

LEA Webinar 8: Live from the BETT show 2019

- **Webinar 9:** Wednesday, 13 February 2019

Topic: **What is a PIN?**

Experts: Ellinor Wallin (EUPK) and Kati Clements (JYU)

LEA Webinar 9: What is a Prior Information Notice (PIN)?

- **Webinar 10:** Wednesday, 20 February 2019

Topic: **LEA school lab experiences: Sweden, Italy, Finland, Portugal, and Germany.**

Experts: R. Ström, I. Calvagna, P. Huuska, A. Direito, P. Schüssler

LEA Webinar 10: LEA School Labs, Autumn 2018

- **Webinar 11:** Wednesday, 20 March 2019

Topic: **Information on how to use the Procurement Forum**

Expert: Ashleigh McLennan

LEA Webinar 11: How to use the Procurement Forum

Future webinars:

- **Webinar 13:** Date to be announced

Topic: **Open Market Consultation Methodology**

Expert: To be announced

- **Webinar 14:** 22 May 2019 (planned)

Topic: **Artificial Intelligence in Education**

Expert: Fabrizio Cardinali

- **Webinar 15:** 05 June 2019 (planned)

Topic: **Changing the assessment culture in schools through analytics**

Expert: Markus Packalen, Qri

2.4 CBS Satisfaction Evaluation Survey

Like in the first internal CBS, a survey was carried on after each external CBS, in order to assess the participants' satisfaction and to improve the next CBS activities and contents. A Satisfaction Evaluation Survey was delivered to the participants by email, at the end of the CBS held at *Festival dell'Educazione* in Turin (Italy) and at the end of the CBS held at *INTED2019* in Valencia (Spain).

At the CBS in Turin, 25 persons attended, and 8 answered the questionnaire. At the CBS in Valencia, around 20-25 persons attended, and 7 answered the questionnaire. The questions and the results are presented below (see questionnaire on annexes).

1. In which group do you include yourself in?

a) CBS Festival dell'Educazione

At this CBS, it was possible to gather participants from the 4 groups previewed in the questionnaire. More than one third of the individuals that answered the questionnaire were Learning Technology Experts (38%), followed by the Procurers (25%), Legal PCP/PPI and Dissemination Experts (25%) and Network Experts (13%).

b) CBS INTED2019

From the CBS organised within INTED2019, 43% of the individuals that answered the questionnaire were Procurers, 29% were Network Experts and 29% were Legal PCP/PPC and Dissemination Experts, only missing the Learning Technology Experts.

Graphic 1 – Participants in LEA CBS at the *Festival dell'Educazione* and *INTED 2019*, by area of expertise.

2. How satisfied were you with the CBS?

a) CBS Festival dell'Educazione

Concerning the level of satisfaction, all the participants that had answered are satisfied, being almost 90% completely satisfied.

b) CBS INTED2019

Also, the participants of the CBS organised at INTED2019 revealed to be satisfied with this session: 57% were completely satisfied, 29% were very satisfied and 14% were satisfied.

Graphic 2 – Participants' satisfaction concerning LEA CBS at the *Festival dell'Educazione* and *INTED 2019*

3. Which topics of the CBS did you find more interesting or useful?

a) CBS Festival dell'Educazione

Concerning the 4 main topics on which the CBS at the Festival dell'Educazione focused on, **“Understanding the PCP legal framework and exemption regime”** and **“How to manage and design the PCP”** were the 2 voted as more interesting for the participants, followed by the **“Understanding Innovation Procurement procedures, instruments and approaches”**.

Graphic 3 – Topics more interesting for participants at LEA CBS – Festival dell'Educazione.

When asked to comment the choices, participants highlighted the advanced skills of the “trainer”, as well as the clarity and simplicity of the contents presented as main positive aspects regarding the topic **“Understanding the PCP legal framework and exemption regime”**:

“The presentation was very clear, precise, full of examples, highlighting all the experience in the field and ability to analyze and synthesis of the speaker... real expert, she makes simple what is complex. Happy to learn from her. It has been very useful to ask for advice on specific procurements initiatives we were conducting.”

Concerning the topic **“How to manage and design the PCP”**, participants mentioned that it allowed to better understand the relevance of innovation procurement in their work:

“Very good opportunity for us to meet a very renowned expert and have clear explanations on PCP and PPI directly from her... has convincing us that innovation procurement is the right path!”

Finally, regarding the topic **“Understanding Innovation Procurement procedures, instruments and approaches”**, it was said that it was helpful to clarify the goals and challenges of participants’ future work:

“Understanding Innovation procurement procedure has been important for our future project activity and made clearer which our future goals will be and how challenging for the future.”

Despite of having selected the aforementioned topics as the most relevant, participants consider that all the topics presented were important. In this sense, when participants were asked to comment the topics less relevant, they answered that there was *“no less relevant or interesting topic”*.

b) CBS INTED2019

Taking into account the 5 main topics that were presented on the CBS at INTED2019, the 4 most voted were **“Understanding the innovation procurement: tools to steer the market towards innovative solutions for education”** with 43%, followed by **“Two different procurement partners: Viladecans, Spain, and Konnevesi, Finland – similar visions of digital learning”** with 29% and, finally, both with 14% **“Are we currently moving from the age of mobilism to age of artificial intelligence, learning analytics and robotics? How to couple emergent technology with learning and teaching?”** and **“AI, Robotics, VR – How to make cost effective and sustainable procurement decisions for future technologies in municipalities and schools”**.

Graphic 4 – Topics more interesting for participants at LEA CBS – INTED2019.

The reasons for choosing the topic **“Understanding the innovation procurement”** are related to the ability of the “trainers” to present and discuss the innovation procurement in an understandable way for the audience:

It was “very important to know more about innovation procurement since it is a very hard topic (...) it was very well explained and also illustrated with images that sometimes are worth more than words.”

“The way of presenting the contents was good.”

Concerning the topic **“Two different procurement partners”**, participants mentioned that this presentation gave them another perspective — more practical —, while enabled an important discussion around the motivation to use learning technologies and the use of technology in schools that many times do not even have technological resources/ equipment:

“It was important (...) to know more about specific success cases like IMAILE, it helps us to have another perspective from the more

practical point of view” and also because the link between technology and equipment it is hard ...”

“How to couple technology with learning in schools where there is not enough ICT equipment...this is still truth in many schools. And how to motivate all? That's big question.”

Regarding the presentation **“Are we currently moving from the age of mobilism to age of artificial intelligence, learning analytics and robotics”**, participants stressed that it was relevant and interesting because it enhanced their knowledge around the benefits of technology in education:

“I really like to hear more and learn more on how the new technologies can improve learning and teaching.”

No comments were provided on the presentation **“AI, Robotics, VR – How to make cost effective and sustainable procurement decisions for future technologies in municipalities and schools”**.

Finally, the participants of this CBS also found some difficulty to comment the topics less relevant to them. In their opinion, all the topics presented were *“some way important and interesting”*.

4. How satisfied were you with the trainers?

a) CBS Festival dell'Educazione

Concerning the satisfaction with the trainers, almost 90% of the participants were completely satisfied and nearly 10% said that they were just satisfied.

b) CBS INTED2019

The general opinion regarding the trainers at CBS INTED2019 is also very positive: 57% of the participants were very satisfied and 43% completely satisfied.

Graphic 5 – Participants' satisfaction concerning the "trainers" of LEA CBS at the Festival dell'Educazione and INTED 2019

5. How do you think the CBS could have been made more effective?

About suggestions to improve the effectiveness of the CBS, the most referred suggestions on both seminars were:

- More time dedicated to some practical exercises and examples;
- More time dedicated do Questions and Answers;
- Extension of the CBS duration (for instance with half-day duration)

6. How satisfied were you with the organization of the CBS, considering venue and duration?

a) CBS Festival dell'Educazione

The participants of the CBS Festival dell'Educazione evaluate positively the organisation of this CBS: 50% of the attendees that answered the questionnaire were very satisfied and 50% were completely satisfied.

b) CBS INTED2019

Concerning the organisation of the CBS INTED2019, the evaluations given by the participants are also positive: 29% of the participants mentioned that they were completely satisfied, 57% were very satisfied and 14% were satisfied.

Graphic 6 – Participants' satisfaction concerning the organization (venue and duration) of LEA CBS at the Festival dell'Educazione and INTED 2019

7. Which other PCP/PPI themes would you like to be presented on the following CBS (also including webinars)?

a) CBS Festival dell'Educazione

When asked to choose the themes that they would like to be presented and discussed during future CBS and webinars, the participants of the CBS Festival dell'Educazione chose mainly the following themes:

1. Steps for PCP preparation – Short presentation of successful cases
2. How to build a business case for an innovation procurement
3. Steps for PPI preparation - Short presentation of successful cases

Graphic 7 – Themes that participants of LEA CBS – Festival dell'Educazione would like to be discussed in the next LEA CBS/ webinars.

b) CBS INTED2019

The participants of CBS INTED2019 chose mainly the following themes to be presented in future sessions:

1. Steps for PPI preparation – Short presentation of successful cases
2. Steps for PCP preparation – Short presentation of successful cases
3. Understanding the legal framework - How to manage the PCP-PPI link

These results seem to be aligned with the suggestion of having more practical examples, since on these presentations real examples of other PCP and PPI projects are presented. On both CBS the themes **Steps for PPI preparation – Short presentation of successful cases** and **Steps for PCP preparation – Short presentation of successful cases** were chose.

The only difference on the 3 most voted themes was that on *Festival dell Educazione* the theme **How to build a business case for an innovation procurement** it was chose by a participant from the Learning Technology expert group and on *INTED* it was chose **Understanding the legal framework - How to manage the PCP-PPI link** by representatives from the Procurers and Legal PCP/PPI and Dissemination experts groups, what reinforce our previous recommendation that the CBS content needs to be flexible and adaptable according to the type of stakeholders present.

Graphic 8 – Themes that participants of LEA CBS – INTED2019 would like to be discussed in the next LEA CBS/ webinars.

8. Comments and suggestions (including activities or initiatives you think would be useful, for the future).

In the final of the questionnaire, the participants were asked to provide further comments and suggestions. Gathering the valid suggestions from the two CBS the following could be summarised:

- More time for discussion between the participant and with the experts, with time for Q&A;
- More involvement of local, national stakeholders;
- Presentation of more successful business cases;
- Having a longer seminar, such as a half-day seminar;
- More practical exercises.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE CBS

CBS are one of the activities previewed by LEA project to engage the stakeholders (especially procurers) into the LEARNTECH accelerator community. Two external CBS were organised until April 2019, both within the framework of larger events (*Festival dell'Educazione* and *INTED2019*), in order to get the attention and involvement of the highest number of participants possible. Their content and structure took into account the recommendations resulting from the evaluation of the first CBS: the topics discussed were diverse, adjusted to each context and presented in a clear and simple format, and it was offered time to Questions and Answers from the participants.

At the *Festival dell'Educazione*, the CBS assumed the form of a workshop and had 25 attendees. At *INTED2019*, the CBS was accepted to be

included into the programme as a special session and had about 20-25 attendees.

At the end of each CBS, the opinion of the participants was collected by delivering them a satisfaction survey: 8 participants answered the questionnaire from the CBS Festival dell'Educazione, and 7 participants answered from the CBS INTED2019.

From the answers collected, it was possible to recognise that both CBS had the participation of different type of stakeholders (Procurers; Learning Technology Experts; Legal PCP/PPI and Dissemination Experts; and Network Experts). In general, the participants revealed to be very satisfied with the two CBS, concerning its contents, "trainers" and organisation (duration and venue).

3.1 Recommendations/Guidelines for future CBS

Following the suggestions given by the participants of the two CBS, as well as the feed-back of the trainers, we were able to build a few guidelines/recommendations that will help us on the organisation of future CBS, namely the two already planned for being held during 2019.

Concerning CBS Structure and organization

- The CBS total duration should be reconsidered, opting for a half-day seminar, including more hands-on exercises with the participants and more time for Q&A;
- For the CBS analysed in this document, the strategy chosen was to organise seminars within two existing events, Festival dell' Educazione and INTED2019, trying with this approach to gather more participants to the CBS. Although on both seminars the 25 required participants were reached, we think the number of participants could be improved. In this sense, for future CBS, it will be explored another approach to increase the number of participants, specifically the CBS will be upon invitation and pre-registration on the event. With this approach we expect to guarantee reaching all the 4 groups of relevant stakeholders. Besides, it shall allow to monitor the number and type of participants and improve the preparation and adjustment of the CBS accordingly;
- Aligned with the physical CBS, a series of webinars have been presented regularly, which has proved to be a good combination with the physical seminars, since people can either assist them directly and/or revisit them whenever they want, posting questions directly on the presentations on the LEA's Youtube channel.

Concerning CBS Contents

- Try to include as much successful business cases from PCP and/or PPI as possible, since it revealed to be a very valuable asset for the participants;
- Keep the content of the CBS flexible and adaptable according to the type and level of knowledge of public and event, always used the developed materials in the best suitable way for the participants;
- Extra efforts to include practical and real-life examples in the presentations, and whenever possible having them presented by local/national stakeholders who were directly involved in the case.

Concerning CBS Evaluation

- Satisfaction Evaluation Surveys did not get the participation expected from the public. Additional efforts should be carried out to increase the answers of the surveys and/or other techniques (real time voting system during the session) should be considered to assess the participants' satisfaction on CBS;
- In the Survey, instead of asking individuals to select the most relevant topic presented, ask individuals to rank the topics from the most relevant to the less relevant, as this can give a more accurate evaluation from the participants.

4. ANNEXES

LEA - Capacity building Seminar - Festival dell'Educazione

Please kindly provide us your opinion and perception of the LEA CBS. This will help us improve the next CBS.

Answers are anonymous and according to GPRD.

***Obrigatório**

1. How satisfied were you with the CBS?

Choose only one option. (1-completely unsatisfied; 2-unsatisfied; 3-satisfied; 4-very satisfied; 5-completely satisfied)

1 2 3 4 5

completely unsatisfied completely satisfied

2. Which topics of the CBS did you find more interesting or useful?

Choose only one option.

- Innovation policy mix
- Understanding Innovation Procurement procedures, instruments and approaches
- Understanding the PCP legal framework and exemption regime
- How to manage and design the PCP

3. Please provide comments on the topics that you have found MORE relevant or interesting.

A sua resposta

4. Please provide comments on the topics that you have found LESS relevant or interesting.

A sua resposta

5. How satisfied were you with the trainers?

Choose only one option (1-completely unsatisfied; 2-unsatisfied; 3-satisfied; 4-very satisfied; 5-completely satisfied).

- 1 2 3 4 5
- Completely Unsatisfied Completely Satisfied

6. How do you think the CBS could have been made more effective?

A sua resposta

7. How satisfied were you with the organization of the CBS, considering venue and duration.

Choose only one option (1-completely unsatisfied; 2-unsatisfied; 3-satisfied; 4-very satisfied; 5-completely satisfied).

1 2 3 4 5

Completely Unsatisfied Completely Satisfied

8. Which other PPI themes would you like to be presented on the following CBS (also including webinars)?

Check all that apply.

- Steps for PCP preparation – Short presentation of successful cases
- Steps for PPI preparation - Short presentation of successful cases
- Steps for PCP/PPI preparation – How to define awarding criteria
- How to deal and secure the rules on IPR
- How to face the lock-in problem and the approach to open standard based solutions in LEA domain
- How to build a business case for an innovation procurement

9. Comments and suggestions (including activities or initiatives you think would be useful, for the future).

A sua resposta

10. Please select the group you include yourself in *

Choose only one option.

- Procurers
- Learning Technology Expert
- Networks
- Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Expert

LEA - Capacity building Seminar - INTED2019

Please kindly provide us your opinion and perception of the LEA CBS. This will help us improve the next CBS.

Answers are anonymous and according to GPRD.

*Obrigatório

1. How satisfied were you with the CBS?

Choose only one option. (1-completely unsatisfied; 2-unsatisfied; 3-satisfied; 4-very satisfied; 5-completely satisfied)

	1	2	3	4	5	
completely unsatisfied	<input type="radio"/>	completely satisfied				

2. Which topics of the CBS did you find more interesting or useful?

Choose only one option.

- Understanding the innovation procurement: tools to steer the market towards innovative solutions for education
- Two different procurement partners: Viladecans, Spain, and Konnevesi, Finland – similar visions of digital learning
- Needs analysis for ICT in teaching and learning
- AI, Robotics, VR – How to make cost effective and sustainable procurement decisions for future technologies in municipalities and schools
- Are we currently moving from the age of mobilism to age of artificial intelligence, learning analytics and robotics? How to couple emergent technology with learning and teaching?

3. Please provide comments on the topics that you have found MORE relevant or interesting.

A sua resposta

4. Please provide comments on the topics that you have found LESS relevant or interesting.

A sua resposta

5. How satisfied were you with the trainers?

Choose only one option (1-completely unsatisfied; 2-unsatisfied; 3-satisfied; 4-very satisfied; 5-completely satisfied).

1 2 3 4 5

Completely Unsatisfied Completely Satisfied

6. How do you think the CBS could have been made more effective?

A sua resposta

7. How satisfied were you with the organization of the CBS, considering venue and duration.

Choose only one option (1-completely unsatisfied; 2-unsatisfied; 3-satisfied; 4-very satisfied; 5-completely satisfied).

1 2 3 4 5

Completely Unsatisfied

Completely Satisfied

8. Which other PCP/PPI themes would you like to be presented on the following CBS (also including webinars)?

Check all that apply.

- Steps for PCP preparation – Short presentation of successful cases
- Steps for PPI preparation - Short presentation of successful cases
- Steps for PCP/PPI preparation – How to define awarding criteria
- Understanding the legal framework - How to deal and secure the rules on IPR
- Steps for PCP/PPI preparation –How to face the lock-in problem and the approach to open standard based solutions in LEA domain
- Steps for PCP/PPI preparation –How to build a business case for an innovation procurement
- Understanding the PCP legal framework and exemption regime
- Steps for PCP/PPI preparation - Open Market consultation
- Understanding the legal framework - How to manage the PCP-PPI link

9. Comments and suggestions (including activities or initiatives you think would be useful, for the future).

A sua resposta

10. Please select the group you include yourself in *

Choose only one option.

- Procurers
- Learning Technology Expert
- Networks
- Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Expert

